

RENDU-OSLER-WEBER SYNDROME WITH BIG PULMONARY ARTERO-VEINOUS MALFORMATION (PAVM) AND ASSOCIATED FORAMEN OVALE PATENCY (FOP)

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ABSTRACT A 55 years old woman with a personal history of brain abscesses, recurrent epistaxis and transient ischemic attacks, underwent Mininvasive Surgery with atrial septal device positioning. Due to further brain abscesses and transient ischemic attacks, subsequent diagnostic studies were carried out, and a large Pulmonary Arteriovenous Malformation (PAVM) was diagnosed. The presence of 3 of the 4 Curaçao criteria makes the diagnosis of Rendu-Osler-Weber Syndrome.

KEYWORDS PAVM, FOP, Rendu-Osler-Weber Syndrome

Background

A 55-years-old woman with a family history of Foramen Ovale Patency (FOP) and epistaxis (mother and daughter), personal history of brain abscesses, recurrent epistaxis and transient ischemic attacks, underwent Mininvasive Surgery with atrial septal device positioning. Due to further brain abscesses and transient ischemic attacks, subsequent diagnostic studies (Chest CT scan in particular) were carried out, and a large Pulmonary Arteriovenous Malformation (PAVM) was diagnosed (Fig 1). The presence of 3 of the 4 Curaçao criteria [1] (epistaxis, AVM visceral lesions and family history) make the diagnosis of Rendu-Osler-Weber Syndrome, also called Hereditary Hemorrhagic Telangiectasia. The patient refused minimally invasive treatment, and we made a successful videothoracoscopic resection of the AVM (Fig 2).

Competing Interests

None

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Figure 1: CT scan and 3D reconstruction showing the AVM (marked with an asterisk). A) axial section. B) coronal section. C) 3D reconstruction showing perfectly the AVM with the abnormal vein (black arrows) and artery (white arrows).

Figure 2: The removed AVM with the abnormal artery (white arrow) and vein (black arrow).

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References

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